
Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following guidelines and styles:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure, for example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg ha/N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example 20 kg ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviation in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were... or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in ...
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example, six parts: seven tractors: four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Outcrossing potential of a cyto-sterile stock of rice

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Successful development and production of hybrid rice in the People's Republic of China (PROC) have encouraged rice breeders to explore hybrid technology in the tropics. For the approach to be viable, economic seed production is imperative. Cost of hybrid seed depends on natural cross-pollination and seed set potential of cyto-sterile (C-ms) stocks used for seed increase of male steriles (ms) or for seed production. We evaluated outcrossing potential of V 20A C-ms under open pollination during 1981 and 1982 dry seasons.

V 20B (pollinator) seedlings were planted in a 12- × 20-m isolated plot at 15- × 20-cm spacing in 1982 dry season. (The 1981 plot was smaller.) Three seedlings, aged 1, 2, and 3 weeks, were transplanted to each hill to provide male sterile plants a substantial pollen load for 2-3 weeks. V 20A C-ms seedlings replaced pollinator plants in every 7th hill, providing 1 cyto-sterile plant for 1.44-m² planted area, or a 1:48 to pollinator plants.

Extent of outcrossing on ms plants located between pollinator plants was estimated by counting the seeds set on the panicles of all the ms plants. Data are presented as percentage of seed set (see table). Seed set varied with individual plants. However, the two dry seasons differed little in mean percentage of seed set on ms plants (22.6% in 1981 and 26.3% in 1982). Close examination of C-ms panicles showed about one-third of the basal region florets did not set seed because this portion of the panicle lacked exertion and because the flag leaf was physically hindered.

Seed set data were reanalyzed to estimate seed set potential through open pollination alone by subtracting number

Percentage seed set on V 20A cyto-sterile plants through open pollination using V 20B pollinator, Cuttack, India.

Year	Cyto-sterile plants (no.)	Mean seed set (%)	Mean seed set (%) on exerted panicle
1981	36	22.68	29.33
1982	95	26.31	31.14

of florets in the boot leaf sheath. This analysis estimated seed set to be 29.3% and 31.1% for the two seasons, an encouraging statistic. Perhaps using gibberellic acid spray at panicle initiation could give a 5% increase in natural seed set. Supplemental pollination, flag leaf clipping, and synchronized flowering, as used in hybrid seed production plots in PROC, may enhance the C-ms seed set potential on open pollination.

Performance of new BW rice varieties under farmer-managed conditions

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BW rice varieties developed at the Bombuwela research station for problem areas in Low Country wet zones were tested during April-July 1981.

BW272-6B was tested in bog and half-bog soils where farmers usually grow Herath Banda, a low yielding local variety. BW267-3 was evaluated where severe iron toxicity is prevalent. BW266-7 was studied where gall midge damages crops.

Farmers were given seed but they determined land preparation and management techniques, including fertilizer and agrochemical application.

In selected fields, 375-m² plots were marked. Harvesting was by crop-cutting survey, supervised by field trial researchers. Three 18-m² plots were harvested from within the larger plots.

BW variety yields in selected Low Country Wet Zone locations, Bombuwela, Sri Lanka.

Variety	District	Locations (no.)	Av yield (t/ha)
BW272-6B	Kalutara Galle	23	2.12
BW267-3	Kalutara Galle Gampaha Matara Rathnapura Colombo	37	3.13
BW266-7	Rathnapura	03	2.65

A natural rice mutant from IR22

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Natural or spontaneous mutants in rice occur infrequently and are usually lethal. A mutant has been isolated from an IR22 multiplication plot at the Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal, India. Leaves have no auricle, ligule, or junctura.

The mutant was protected from pollen contamination and seeds obtained were grown the following season to test previous observations. Reciprocal crosses were made between IR22 and the mutant. F₁ plants were scored for auricle, ligule, and junctura characteristics 4 weeks after sowing. The progeny exhibited all three leaf characteristics, indicating dominance. F₂ populations showed segregation patterns conforming to monogenic control of the characteristics (see table).

Distribution frequencies of F₂ population.

Auricle, ligule and junctura		X ² value
Present	Absent	
610	214	0.364 <i>p</i> = 0.70 – 0.50

The mutant's leaves grow at an acute angle. Studies are in progress to determine if this leaf arrangement captures more solar radiation and allows higher nutrient uptake rates.

All varieties proved successful when used with low inputs in the Low Country wet zone (see table). BW272-6B yielded 2.12 t/ha, nearly twice the Herath Banda yield of 1.44 t/ha. It was well adapted to bog and half-bog soils.

An early dwarf mutant of Tilakchandan

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Tilakchandan is a popular rice variety in northwestern Uttar Pradesh. It has excellent cooking qualities and mild aroma. It is a traditional tall, photoperiod-sensitive, late-maturing variety (150-155 days). Use is decreasing because the variety is not efficient in

Table 1. Morphological and grain characteristics of Tilakchandan and its mutant, West Bengal, India

Characteristic	Tilakchandan	Mutant
Height (cm)	125	85
50% flowering (days)	122	82
Av no. of tillers/hill	18	18
Position of flag leaf	Erect	Erect
Plant type	Tall	Dwarf
Panicle length (cm)	25.8	23.6
Grains per panicle	169.8	101.4
Awned or awnless	Awned	Awned
1,000-grain weight	16.7	13.6
Kernel length (mm)	5.0	5.6
Kernel width (mm)	2.0	2.0
Length-breadth ratio	2.5	2.8
Rice color	White	White
Abdominal white	Absent	Absent
Hulling (%)	76.0	75.0
Milling (%)	72.0	70.5
Alkali value	4.1	2.5
Kernel elongation	2.1	2.3
Volume expansion	5.8	5.1
Water uptake (at boiling temp)	600	520
Cooking quality	Good	Good

Table 2. Yield performance of Tilakchandan and its mutant in scented variety trials, 1979 and 1980 kharif, West Bengal, India.^a

Variety	Yield (kg/ha)						Days to 50% flowering
	Pantnagar		Nagina		Bulandshahr		
	1979	1980	1979	1980	1979	1980	
Tilakchandan (mutant)	1210	2350	2227 ^b	1250	5020*	2917	82
Tilakchandan (normal)	3298*	3856*	1662	2472*	2945	3558	122
C.D. (5%)	1195	684	904	1183	872	821	–
C.V.	29.01	10.20	23.65	17.55	10.12	18.21	–

^a*Significantly higher at 5% level of significance. ^bCrop suffered from drought.

BW267-3 was highly adapted to iron-toxic soils and yielded well. BW266-7 was resistant to gall midge from seedling stage to maximum tillering and produced well.

rice-wheat rotation, which is common in the region.

In 1972 a breeding program was initiated to develop dwarf and early mutants. Dehusked seeds were soaked in distilled water for 6 hours, then treated with freshly prepared EMS aqueous solution in 3 concentrations (0.2%, 0.4% and 0.6%). They were held at room temperature for 6 hours, with intermittent shaking.

Treated seeds were washed in running tap water for 1 hour, then sown on blotting paper at room temperature. Seedlings were moved to a field nursery 7 days after sowing, and transplanted (10 × 20 cm spacing) in the main field 25 days after sowing.

The first three panicles and bulks were separately carried to the M2 generation. Panicle to row planting and, thereafter, single plant progenies were carried from M3 to M6. Productive mutants were isolated, purified, multiplied, and evaluated in multilocation trials.

The selected mutant matured earliest. Qualities were similar to those of Tilakchandan (Table 1). Kernel length and elongation rate were higher than for Tilakchandan. Alkali value and water uptake were slightly lower. Mutant yield was lower because panicles had fewer grains (Table 2). The mutant is dwarf and flowers early. It can be used in hybridization programs. Seed is available to interested breeders.